

TITLE: ACADEMIC STRESS AND ITS EFFECT ON UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Abstract. One of the most common issues among university students is academic stress. Many students face the pressure caused by various factors such as assignment work, exams, deadlines, and the requirement to achieve impressive academic results. This paper explores how academic stress influences academic achievements and the learning process of students. In this research, a quantitative methodology was applied, and data were gathered using a questionnaire distributed among 100 university students. This study examines such aspects as workload, sleep, exam pressure, and stress of students. It is evident that students with higher levels of stress find it difficult to concentrate, manage their time, and attain desirable academic performance. Most respondents experienced sleep difficulties during the exams. On the other hand, students may be motivated to work harder with a reasonable level of stress and act responsibly in the process of learning. The research highlights that time management and appropriate coping strategies help minimize the negative consequences of academic stress. Academic institutions should assist students in both academic and psychological aspects in order to ensure favorable conditions for students' learning process.

Keywords: academic stress, university students, achievement, stress management, higher education

Intraduction. The problem of academic stress can be viewed as one of the key issues of current education systems. Students at university often bear the weight of heavy assignments, workload in several disciplines, multiple deadlines and deadlines for the assignments, examinations stress, and a keen competition. In most cases, particularly in the periods of mid-term and final examinations, the pressure amplifies even more Psychological and physiological stress triggered by an academic environment is defined as academic stress. It relates not only to the amount of work students are assigned but also the strictness of the assignment deadline, lecturer's expectations of the students and the grading schemes which, in many cases are highly competitive. It should be noted that there are situations when students are forced to prepare and hand in two or three assignments for just a short span of time, thus boosting the stress to a greater degree. Several researches indicate that a higher stress rate impairs the ability of students to focus, as well as have a negative effect on the memory. In consequence, students cannot assimilate what they are learning on academic basis fully. Some students also encounter the following consequences of stress; loss of sleep, fatigue, and headache during the examination period. In Uzbekistan students who receive a scholarship are under more pressure as they have to gain a higher grade to maintain the scholarship. However, not all stress can be regarded as being of negative character; it is possible that a small portion of stress before an examination may prompt a student

to prepare better. This study mainly aims to analyze the correlation between the intensity of academic stress and the performance of university student.

Literature Review. Academic stress has been researched widely in higher education recently due to its highly correlation with student's academic achievement and students' well-being. Many scholars investigated on negative and positive impacts of stress, as well as factors leading to students' coping to stress.

Negative Impact of Academic Stress. Lots of studies have shown the negative impacts of academic stress on students. Misra and McKean (2000) also found high stress level reduces the concentration and academic efficiency. Students who perceive their academic stress is high report anxiety, emotional depletion and low academic achievement as shown by Bedewy and Gabriel (2015). Students experiencing high stress are suffered from academic burnout and lack of motivation, therefore performance is likely to be worse shown in the finding of Lin and Huang (2014). Students' lack of control towards academic stress results in damage to academic success of students.

Positive Function of Moderate Stress. Nevertheless, not all the stress is negative shown by Yerkes & Dodson (1908) that a moderate amount of stress can lead to improvement in the performance level through enhanced alertness and motivation. 'Eustress' is also considered a positive outcome to students under a specific pressure level. Struthers, Perry & Menec (2000) found students are likely to gain good academic success if students consider stress is a challenge and not a threat. The way students perceiving stress is also having impact toward them. Causes of Academic Stress Academic stress comes in many ways. Students have several things contributing to the level of stress they feel. According to Kohn & Frazer (1986), the main sources of stress for students are excessive course work and exam preparation. Similarly, Elias, Ping & Abdullah (2011) have noted that procrastination of studies due to poor time management skills, imbalanced academic and personal life and high expectation levels from the teachers raise the level of stress in the students. These causes are particularly applicable to university level, as students have a lot of things on their plate. Coping strategies Students utilize varying coping strategies, and the way students cope has a great impact on academic performance. Researchers have found that problem-focused coping mechanisms (e.g. Plan of action and seeking support) lead to more positive academic outcomes (Carver, Scheier, & Weintraub, 1989) while emotion-focused coping mechanisms (e.g. Avoidance and procrastination) are positively related to greater stress and negative academic performance (Folkman & Lazarus, 1985). This means the way a student copes with their stress is equally important as the amount of stress itself

Critical Analysis

While there is substantial literature addressing the link between academic stress and academic performance, a number of shortcomings are evident in the current body of research. Firstly, the majority of the research has utilized self-reported data and thus relies upon the veracity of the participants' accounts, in which they may underrate or overrate their stress levels. Secondly, most research

has only addressed the negative consequences of stress with limited investigation into the benefits. Furthermore, limited longitudinal studies have been conducted, focusing more on immediate implications rather than the long-term effect that stress has on academic achievement. In addition to this, differences between individual students seem to be overlooked; elements such as an individual's personality type, subject discipline and culture all have effects on their experience of and response to stress. Highly competitive environments, for instance, can induce stress much greater than otherwise. Longitudinal studies should, hence, be further explored along with the consideration of diverse populations and further exploration of the positive consequences of academic stress.

Methodology

A quantitative research design was used for this study. A descriptive and correlational research design was employed to identify relationship between the level of stress of students and their academic achievement. One hundred university students from various faculties were the subjects for this study.

Participants were randomly selected to ensure reliable data obtained and to have a balanced sample size. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire which had the following variables to measure:

- number of assignments per week
- number and time of exams
- number of sleep per night (hours)
- academic achievement (GPA or 100 scale)
- students' perception on their stress level (1-5 likert scale)

The students rated their stress level from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high).

Data were then analyzed using the percentage analysis and correlation. The data was displayed in tables and graphs for the ease of understanding. Some of the participants mentioned that the average number of hours they slept per night during examination weeks has dropped to 4-5 hours only, with the reason that there is a lot of assignment to submit, and the workload of exams and test preparation are high at this time of year.

Results. This study clearly indicates the correlation between academic stress and academic performance.

70% students reported a range from medium to severe level of stress (between the level of 3 to 5)

60% students had problems managing to hand in assignments on time

55% students expressed they were highly stressed and did not sleep well before exams

The analysis of correlation shows that stress and academic performance are inversely related (that means that higher stress levels lead to lower academic performances, the GPA) Students with less stress managed to plan assignments before hand, had good and stable sleeping habits and could gradually prepare for the exams.

Discussion and Conclusion. This study revealed that time management and academic burden is major source of academic stress among the students.

Overlapping assignments and high volume of assignment submission were identified as one of the most stressful situations. A high amount of stress affects a student's ability to concentrate, increases tiredness and lowers their overall academic performance as a stressed student finds it difficult to maintain their focus and discipline. However, at low amount stress may have positive outcome by providing a boost to the students and helping them to stay disciplined and attentive; provided the amount is well managed. Universities must address academic workload balance and should provide workshops and trainings on skills such as time management and stress management to alleviate the pressure on the students. According to my view, the actual problem is not stress, but lack of coping mechanisms and time management and organizational skills among students; by equipping them with this skills we can largely eliminate the negative impact of academic stress.

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